

Fe₂O₃ thin films on deposited on ITO substrate and its RBS characterization

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Abstract

Fe₂O₃ thin film was deposited on the ITO plate by using Thermal evaporation technique. X-ray diffraction (XRD), Rutherford back scattering (RBS), and optical bandgap (BG) of the ITO in Fe₂O₃ system were studied. The optical and structural characteristics of the films were measured. The overall features of these XRD curves confirm the crystalline nature of the present samples and calculated the crystal size of the value nearly 43 nm. The UV-Vis study the band gap of Fe₂O₃ is 3.21 eV. Morphology of Fe₂O₃ presents which gives the better results are taken by AFM. Wave number 1407 cm⁻¹ has the frequency vibrations of Fe₂O₃ samples. Fe₂O₃ and their concentrations ratio which affect the particles average size, thermal evaporation technique gives the different magnetic properties of the deposited sample. Though there is no hysteresis in the experimental curve, the discrepancy between the measured and calculated curves is observed that can be due to a wide distribution of particles size. The hardness and mechanical strength of the particle was analysed.

Keywords; Samarium, Thermal evaporation technique, SEM, AFM and RBS

References

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